

ACCESSIBLE BANKING THROUGH MOBILE SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The internet and the mobile phone – two technological advancements that have profoundly affected human behavior in the last decade – have started to converge. The products of this association are mobile data services. Using a variety of platforms, services are being created to enable mobile devices to perform many activities of the traditional internet, albeit in a reduced format for mobile devices. One area of activity is mobile (m-) banking (one of the first areas of commercial transaction on the wireless internet). Banking is an area that has extended in many different ways in recent years, including telephone and online banking. M-banking provides yet another channel for banking services, and in emerging markets, provides some possibility for becoming a primary channel. This paper examines the strategic implications of m-banking and the strategic positioning of m-banking services in different markets. The paper concludes with a discussion of the future for m-banking services.

Keywords: Mobile commerce; mobile banking; strategy; markets; technology acceptance; benefits.

INTRODUCTION:

In the last decade, we have witnessed the increasing penetration and development of two key areas of technology: the internet and wireless telephony. The internet has proven to be an easy and efficient way of delivering a wide variety of services to millions of ‘wired’ users; as of February 2002, the estimated number of internet users stood at 544 million, rising to 1 billion by 2005. Throughout the 1990s, the mobile phone has also played an increasingly important role in society. Again, this is a technology in an age where time is short and the weight attached to convenience is high. In June 2002, the number of mobile phone users worldwide reached one billion for the first time. In many developed economies, saturation of phone ownership is beginning to occur, as penetration rates reach more than 70% in countries such as the UK, Hong Kong, Japan, Finland and New Zealand.

Some of the first commercial applications of the mobile internet involve wireless or mobile (m-) banking. These developments build on earlier ideas of customer channel extension through telephone banking and online banking. M-banking taps the mobile customer channel in an effort to further reduce costs. In some emerging markets, such as China, where internet penetration is low, m-banking offers the opportunity to break into the online banking channel for the first time. This paper explores developments in m-banking in detail. This is a very new area both in terms of the mobile internet platform and the banking applications that have been developed for it.

Therefore, the paper first provides some background to m-banking technologies, before exploring the strategic implications and benefits of m-banking to the banking sector. The paper concludes with a summary and conclusions on the future impact and likely success of m-banking.

BACKGROUND TO MOBILE BANKING SYSTEM:

By its nature, m-banking is a very new phenomenon. In order to better understand the subject of the analysis in this paper, this section provides a brief outline of some of the salient m-banking platforms and services. The emphasis here is on a strategic understanding rather than a technical understanding of services.

DEFINITION OF MOBILE BANKING:

M-banking can be defined as a channel whereby the customer interacts with a bank via a mobile device, such as a mobile phone or personal digital assistant (PDA). The emphasis is on data communication, and in its strictest form m-banking does not include telephone banking, either in its traditional form of voice dial-up, or through the form of dial-up to a service based on touch tone phones.

M-BANKING PLATFORMS:

The first applications of m-banking were based in Finland. As early as 1992 customers of Merita Nord banker were able to make bill payments and check account balances using a mobile phone (based on GSM – Global Standard for Mobile – networks). More recently, m-banking applications have relied on the development of some key standards for wireless electronic services and expanded to global markets. In general, the platforms used have been the wireless application protocol (WAP) and short message service (SMS). However, in Japan, the i-mode platform, based on compact hypertext markup language (cHTML) (and more recently Java), has been the dominant platform for m-banking. Let us briefly examine each of these platforms in more detail.

WAP BANKING:

WAP is a universal standard for bringing internet-based content and advanced value-added services to wireless devices such as phones and personal digital assistants (PDAs). In order to integrate as seamlessly as possible with the web, WAP sites are hosted on web servers and use the same transmission protocol as web sites; that is hypertext transport protocol (HTTP) [6]. The most important difference between web and WAP sites is the application environment. Whereas a web site is coded mainly using hypertext markup language (HTML), WAP sites use wireless markup language (WML), based on extensible markup language (XML). WAP data flows between the web server and a wireless device in both directions via a gateway that sits between the internet and mobile networks. A wireless

device will send a request for information to a server, and the server will respond by sending packets of data, which are formatted for display on a small screen by a piece of software in the wireless device called a micro browser.

MOBILE BANKING:

Mobile banking was one of the first transaction-enabled services to be provided using the WAP platform, partly based on research into consumer perceptions of these emerging services. Early WAP research by Nokia suggested m-banking was likely to become a primary application of choice for those users most interested in wireless data. Around 60% of Europe's largest banks now offer m-banking services, with nearly all using the WAP platform. In some markets, such as Hong Kong, nearly all large banks, such as HSBC, Dao Heng Bank, Hang Seng Bank and Citibank, offer sophisticated m-banking services. Figure 1 shows some screen shots of a banking customer interacting with a WAP phone. The customer logs into the m-banking WAP service to conduct a variety of m-banking activities. Typically, these include:

- ❖ Checking the balance of their account
- ❖ Transaction enquiry
- ❖ Viewing the last transactions made
- ❖ Checking the status of a cheque number
- ❖ Transferring funds from one account to another (usually only for more advanced m-banks)
- ❖ Requesting a transaction statement
- ❖ Requesting a cheque book
- ❖ Cancelling a service request
- ❖ Checking the status of service requests
- ❖ Changing a password
- ❖ Paying a utility bill or credit card
- ❖ Finding account information, e.g. interest rate

Figure 1 Screen shots of m-banking activities

a. Checking an account balance b. Checking transaction information c. Finding product information

SMS BANKING:

SMS allows text messages of up to 160 characters to be sent to and from mobile handsets via a store-and-forward system. Around 500 SMS billion messages were sent in 2001. Although 95% of this is based on person-to-person communication and voicemail, other services such as e-banking are growing in popularity. However, only around 10% of Europe's largest banks offer SMS banking. This is despite the fact that the majority of phones have SMS capability, but only 10% have WAP capability. In the UK, they include the Cooperative Bank, HSBC and First Direct .

Using SMS, banks can offer a variety of services triggered by the customer sending a message to the customer service centre and receiving messages on their phone. By data input via the phone keypad, customers can typically:

- ❖ check the balance of their account
- ❖ check the status of a cheque number
- ❖ transfer funds from one account to another
- ❖ view the last transactions made (usually three to five)
- ❖ request a transaction statement
- ❖ request a cheque book
- ❖ change a password
- ❖ pay a utility bill (usually only for more advanced m-banks).

STRATEGIC ANALYSIS OF THE M-BANKING SECTOR:

Opportunities for IT-enabled competitive advantage vary widely from one company to another, just as the rules and intensity of competition vary widely from one industry to another. The complexity of the IT management challenge increases considerably when IT penetrates to the heart of a firm's (or industry's) strategy. Thus, in order to understand the impacts of the m-banking we need a comprehensive strategic framework. Porter [19] provides such as framework, arguing that economic and competitive forces in an industry segment, such as the m-banking industry, is the result of five basic forces

- positioning of traditional intra-industry rivals
- threat of new entrants into the industry segment
- threat of substitute products or services
- bargaining power of buyers
- bargaining power of suppliers.

This section aims to provide an analysis of the m-banking service sector from a strategic viewpoint. The purpose of this analysis is to provide some understanding of the key forces impacting on the ability of m-banking to succeed in provision of banking services. For illustration, we will focus on the UK banking sector, although the analysis can be reinterpreted for different markets. The results of such an analysis have distinct implications for practitioners. Figure 2 shows Porter's framework, highlighting some of the key elements for each of the five forces. As we can see, there is strength in each of the forces, emphasising a very strong degree of competition in the provision of m-banking services. Let us examine the framework in more detail.

FIGURE: 2: MARKET ANALYSIS: THE M-BANKING SECTOR

RIVALRY

Banks are the major players in the provision of m-banking services. However, as Egg has shown in the online banking sector, the possibility exists for other players to enter the market offering specific products. Rivalry among banking providers differs from country to country. In the UK, the banking sector is competitive, with a large selection of banks in operation, although mergers and takeovers have essentially narrowed the market for the consumer. In this market, rivalry is not at a cut-throat level, with many banks focusing on building relationships with customers at a young age, rather than trying to lure established customers from competitors.

Alliances are likely to play an important role in developing m-banking services. No single industry alone has what it takes to establish m-banking. In the new mobile digital economy, consumer online services demand that diverse inputs must be combined to create and deliver value. The complementary assets and capabilities of mobile operators, banks, other financial services, infrastructure providers, software developers, network security specialists (such as RSA Security or Verisign) and content providers are likely to play an important role, with banks and operators being at the core.

NEW ENTRANTS

Deregulation in the UK banking industry has meant increased competition for banks. This competition extends to the internet. In the online banking sector, internet-only banks such as Egg have challenged traditional 'bricks and mortar' banks. The same threat of new entrants in the m-banking sector is currently limited; customer perceptions of wireless services are not strong enough to build value in this area and there is a small customer base. Services based on WAP have received an apathetic response in many markets, including the UK.

SUBSTITUTES:

A key threat to the viability of mobile banking is the availability of substitutes for the consumer. In the UK, the retail banking market has created an array of channels for banking services, including telephone, internet and branch banking. Any of these or other channels for interaction of customers with banking service providers must be considered substitutes for m-banking services.

Quite often in business, alternative technologies are seen as substitutes for each other. In reality they can also be seen as complementary. In the eyes of the consumer, presenting multiple channels of service activity by various technologies can sometimes be seen as a series of supportable ways offering alternatives that complement one service; in this case banking. This can strengthen the product overall and enable the technology to be perceived by business as a complement rather than as a substitute.

BUYERS:

Ultimately, customers hold the reins when comes to channel selection. The banking sector tends to be based on a customer-centric model, where the emphasis is on managing customer relationships and meeting consumers' increasing levels of sophistication. Buyer power is increasing through deregulation and the provision of internet banking solutions, although mergers and takeover are a

further trend that has helped to reduce customer choice. The problems associated with branch closures in the UK and Ireland underline how customer behaviour is difficult to change. A variety of banks closed branches in remote areas, expecting customers to use other branches. In fact, customers protested, many affected customers moved to other banks, and a number of branches were reopened. Customers in banking are generally very localized, and although switching costs are not particularly high in the traditional market, banks exert extra costs by making such a move difficult (for example, difficulty in closing bank accounts or transferring automatic payments).

SUPPLIERS:

The main suppliers of wireless banking services are the parent banks. However, the companies involved in operating mobile services, providing the infrastructure (hardware and software) and developing content are also an important part of the value chain. Without appropriate competencies in the development and supply of mobile services, banks cannot reach the consumer market. The costs of obtaining such resources balanced against predicted demand is a major determinant of the banks provision of m-banking services. This market is currently reasonably competitive, with a variety of operators competing for added value in the face of falling average revenue per customer. However, operators are beginning to leverage their infrastructure advantages in transport to enable movement along the value chain towards mobile services, delivery support and market making. Consolidation through merger and acquisition in this market is another trend.

Overall, the m-banking sector is very immature. It is subject to a variety of industry forces that could each play an important part in determining the future structure of competition. Customers, in accord with developing needs, are a powerful determinant of the success of this new banking channel over existing channels. As the sector develops, competition is likely to be created through rivalry from banks, potential new entrants from finance and telecommunications, and the increasingly powerful role of suppliers (especially operators and infrastructure providers)

GENERAL MODEL OF TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE:

The model provides an interesting framework for analyzing the potential of m-banking services. By assessing the attitudes and subjective norms associated with using the technology we are better equipped to examine aspects of the likely diffusion of m-banking in different markets.

RELATIVE ADVANTAGE:

A unique value proposition of m-banking services is that they are available ‘on the move’. Many other aspects of the service, such as those of interactivity and remote access are not unique. The relative advantage of m-banking is strongly dependent on existing banking services, electronic or otherwise. For example, m-banking in emerging markets – such as China or India – creates a principal source of relative advantage from the fact that it provides an access channel to many individuals for whom online banking was effectively previously inaccessible. M-banking provides the potential for low-cost access to remote banking services.

COMPLEXITY:

The complexity of m-banking is dictated by the available technological infrastructure and usability of m-banking services. Present technological constraints include low power, difficulties in data input and small screens for handheld devices (as well as high latency and low bandwidth for most

existing services). In areas where traditional online access is available, the use of such devices is likely to be considered more complex and less satisfactory than online banking.

COMPATIBILITY:

The compatibility of m-banking with a customer's experiences and behaviour varies widely between different markets. A key part of this is the user's experience with other technologies and services. This could be in terms of the penetration of mobile phones, PCs, online banking, telephone banking, SMS, i-mode or WAP. For example, if the penetration of mobile phones is high and SMS is a popular service, this could provide a hook for SMS-based m-banking. Where communities are localised and the use of mobile telecommunications is low, the possibilities for m-banking may be more limited.

TRIABILITY:

Most market research conducted in developed economies shows that customers are understandably unwilling to pay for mobile services (e.g. account balances) that they already receive free through another channel; customers, however, are more willing to pay for mobile transaction services such as stock trading and for new pushed services that they could not receive any other way. Nevertheless, advanced mobile banking services, even where they have been provided free of charge, such as in Brazil and Turkey, have experienced relatively low customer take-up. Trialability and pricing of services is likely to be an important part of establishing m-banking and building a critical mass.

OBSERVABILITY:

The immediacy of m-banking services creates a relatively high level of observability. M-banking usage is highly interactive, and, on some services, such as SMS and packet-switched network browsing, transactions are responded to almost instantly. Observability can be enhanced through individuals witnessing others using m-banking, especially since usage on mobile phones and PDAs often occurs 'out in the open'. However, unless contact is made with the user by the observer, it is often very difficult to establish what a device is being used for, and the security aspects of such services must also be observed. Observability is lessened somewhat due to the fact that some important aspects of the innovation, such as the network, are less visible. On the other hand, m-banking usage can form the basis for observable behaviour; for example, after a user checks a bank balance they may reorganise their finances, perhaps transferring money between accounts.

CONCLUSIONS:

Mobile banking is still an immature product. The successful adoption and use of m-banking services is dependent on a number of factors, including existing banking channels, market conditions and customer perceptions. Section three examined the adoption of m-banking services using technology acceptance theory, underlining some of the key aspects of the technology and user behaviour that are likely to play a role in the future adoption of m-banking services. The next five years will provide important evidence regarding the future potential of m-banking in existing and emerging markets. If industry analysts are correct, 2003 is likely to provide the inflection point for the growth of wireless data services, based on the penetration of cheaper data access via packet-switched networks (typically, the global packet radio service or GPRS) and the continued success of platforms such as SMS and its successor, MMS (multimedia message service). Alongside, the growth of short-range wireless services, such as Bluetooth, could provide important complementary platforms for wireless financial services, especially electronic payment at POS.

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